

We are thrilled to collaborate with a wide range of exciting and groundbreaking projects. Learn about their latest news!

AI PRISM

AI-PRISM combines AI, robotics, and social sciences to enhance manufacturing processes in SMEs. The project aims to create synergy between humans and robots to revolutionize the current manufacturing paradigm.

Get to know the project: <https://aiprism.eu/>

StandICT

The first StandICT 2026 Open Call has just been published!

The calls will allocate € 2,925,000 in much-needed funding to support European Standardization specialists working on ICT standards, participate in and bring a European perspective to international and global SDOs, through the StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme.

Learn more: <https://www.standict.eu/news/standicteu-2026-first-open-calls>

ARCADIAN-IoT

This September, the ARCADIAN-IoT Summer School will open its doors in Stockholm to offer PhD students and young researchers an

in-depth exploration of the ever-evolving landscape of IoT cybersecurity. The goal of the summer school is to provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in the field of IoT cybersecurity and to equip them with the knowledge and skills required to tackle current and future security challenges in IoT. The school will issue a participation certificate that can be used to get ETCS from universities.

Registration: <https://www.arcadian-iot.eu/summerschool/>

Co-funded by
the European Union